

Exploring the Discrepancies between SMPS and AMS Measurements in Secondary Organic Aerosol Formation Experiments

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Abstract

Inconsistencies have often been observed between the measurements obtained from the Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS) and the Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) during laboratory experiments focused on secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation. We show that these discrepancies are due to the use of a size-independent collection efficiency (CE) especially in experiments in which new particle formation takes place. A new methodology for the estimation of a composition and size-dependent CE is proposed. This approach significantly improves the agreement between the measurements from the two instruments with the average deviation of the two types of measurements remaining below 10% for both total aerosol and SOA concentration. We show that in these experiments, ammonium sulfate particles both pure and thinly coated with SOA have a lower CE than the pure SOA particles or particles thickly coated with SOA.

1. Introduction

Atmospheric fine particulate matter contains thousands of organic compounds that constitute a significant fraction of its mass (Kanakidou et al., 2005). Organic aerosol (OA) can be emitted by transportation, biomass burning, cooking and other anthropogenic activities as well as biogenic sources. Secondary organic aerosol (SOA) is formed during the oxidation of volatile (VOCs), intermediate volatility (IVOCs) and semivolatile organic compounds (SVOCs) that yield lower volatility products, a fraction of which is

transported to the particulate phase. SOA is often the dominant component of OA in both urban and background areas, and can have serious impacts on human health, visibility, and climate (Zhang et al., 2007; Tkacik et al., 2012). Laboratory experiments in atmospheric simulation chambers have been one of the major sources of data for SOA formation (Doussin et al., 2023). Real-time instruments that can continuously gather information about the properties, concentration and composition of particles are vital for these efforts (Fröhlich et al., 2013). The Aerodyne Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS) (Jayne et al. 2000) can measure in real time, the chemical composition of submicrometer non-refractory (i.e., organics, sulfate, ammonium, chloride, nitrate, and water) aerosol and can quantify the mass distribution of each of these components (DeCarlo et al., 2006).

A fraction of the sampled aerosol mass is not detected by the AMS even when the aerosol does not contain refractory components. Therefore, to correct the AMS measurements, the use of a collection efficiency (CE) is necessary. The CE is defined as the fraction of particle mass detected by the AMS compared to the amount introduced into the AMS inlet (Alfarra et al., 2004).

Prior field (Allan et al., 2004; Quinn et al., 2006) and laboratory experiments (Matthew et al., 2008) revealed that the AMS CE is primarily determined by the particle phase state with the CE of liquid particles being higher than the CE of solid ones. Allan et al. (2004) showed that there is a dependence of the CE on relative humidity (RH) in the AMS inlet as liquid particles tend to be more spherical, resulting this way in a better focusing on the vaporizer by the aerodynamic lens. The particle bounce and thus CE depends also indirectly on particle acidity, with acidic particles having a higher CE than neutral ones (Quinn et al. 2006). Crosier et al. (2007) observed an effect of the nitrate concentration on the CE, reporting a linear increase of the CE with the increase of their nitrate content. Middlebrook et al. (2012) proposed an algorithm for field measurements that parameterizes both the effects of the nitrate content and acidity of particles on the CE. An early laboratory study of Bahreini et al. (2005) observed an increase of the sulfate concentration reported by the AMS when SOA formation started. This apparent increase of sulfate, without reactions producing it, was attributed to the SOA condensation that leads to the formation of an SOA coating on the ammonium sulfate seeds and the reduction of their bouncing on the AMS vaporizer. Matthew et al. (2008) found that the particle impact on the vaporizer is influenced by the sampling RH, the particle water and ammonium nitrate content. They also investigated the presence of the coating thickness of solid particles, observing 100% CE for thickly coated particles and intermediate CEs for thinly coated

solid particles and even lower CEs for pure solid particles. Docherty et al. (2013) concluded that the AMS CE in laboratory experiments strongly depends on particle bounce and linked the CE to the oxidation state of SOA. Docherty et al. (2013) reported CE decreases as the SOA is getting more oxidized.

The most common technique to characterize the CE is by comparing the measurements of AMS with the corresponding ones of other collocated instruments. Particle-into-liquid sampling (PILS) with ion chromatography (Weber et al., 2001; Takegawa et al., 2005) and organic carbon (OC) analyzers (Takegawa et al., 2005) have been used to compare the measured mass loading of individual species. Scanning mobility particle sizers (SMPS) (Kostenidou et al., 2007) and tapered element oscillating microbalances (TEOM) (Allan et al., 2004; Drewnick et al., 2004; Högrefe et al., 2004; Weimer et al., 2006) can be also used for comparing total concentrations. A light scattering module in the AMS has also been used but with limited success (Cross et al., 2009; Slowik et al., 2010).

Kostenidou et al. (2007) developed an algorithm that combines size distribution measurements of an SMPS and an AMS to estimate the CE and therefore to correct the AMS measurements. Using the same algorithm, the SOA density can be estimated. The algorithm combines the volume distribution measured by the SMPS and the mass distributions of the various aerosol components measured by the AMS to estimate the unknown CE and SOA density. This algorithm assumes implicitly that the CE is size independent.

Despite this progress there appear to be cases in which the AMS measurements and the SMPS ones are inconsistent with each other during laboratory SOA formation experiments (Sippial et al., 2023). In this work, we explore the discrepancies between SMPS and AMS measurements during SOA formation experiments that were conducted in two atmospheric simulation chambers. For this purpose, nonylcyclohexane, an anthropogenic cyclic alkane, and α -humulene, a naturally emitted sesquiterpene, were utilized as SOA precursors. Our observations led us to the development of a new approach for the estimation of a size and composition dependent CE.

2. Instrumentation and experimental procedure

Experiments were conducted in two different smog chambers, to test the applicability of the proposed methodology. The atmospheric simulation chamber of the Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas (FORTH-ASC) and the chamber of Carnegie Mellon University (CMU) were the two facilities used. Both chambers are 10 m³ Teflon reactors

located inside temperature-controlled rooms with UV lights covering their walls. The particle number and volume distributions were measured using a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS). At FORTH-ASC, the SMPS included a TSI classifier model 3080, while at CMU, a model 3082. Both instruments were equipped with a differential mobility analyzer (DMA) (TSI model 3081) and a condensation particle counter (CPC) (TSI model 3775). The particle mass and composition were quantified with a high-resolution time of flight aerosol mass spectrometer (HR-ToF-AMS). A Proton-Transfer-Reaction-Mass-Spectrometer (PTR-MS) was used to monitor online the concentration of VOCs. A PTR-QMS 500 (Ionicon Analytik) was used at the FORTH-ASC chamber and PTR-QMG 422 (Ionicon Analytik) at CMU.

In FORTH-ASC, SOA was produced from the reaction of nonylcyclohexane with hydroxyl radicals (OH), under high NO_x conditions encountered in urban areas. In the CMU chamber, a-humulene reacted with ozone (O₃) under practically zero NO_x levels and dark conditions to produce SOA.

Both chambers were flushed with purified dry air for at least 12 hours prior to each experiment. The clean air stream was ambient compressed air that passed through a series of filters that included a high-efficiency particulate air filter (HEPA) for removing particles, activated-carbon filters to remove gas-phase organics, a Purafil filter to remove NO_x and a silica gel filter to remove water vapor.

After filling the reactors, an atomizer (model 3076, TSI) was used to generate ammonium sulfate particles from a solution of 1 g L⁻¹ (NH₄)₂SO₄ in ultrapure water. The resulting droplets passed through a diffusion dryer filled with silica gel and water evaporated before entering the corresponding chamber. The role of the seed aerosol is to provide a surface onto which the organic reaction products can condense as SOA instead of getting lost to the walls. The losses of particles on the chamber walls were characterized in each experiment by leaving the chamber undisturbed for 2 h after the injection of the seeds. In the experiments conducted in FORTH-ASC isotopically labelled butanol (1-butanol-d9) was introduced as an OH tracer. 2-butanol was bubbled into the CMU chamber, functioning as an OH scavenger to prevent the oxidation of the sesquiterpene by the OH radical produced during the ozonolysis reaction. After the VOC precursor injection HONO was added to the FORTH-ASC chamber, using a bubbler, the rapid photolysis of which leads to the production of OH radicals that react with the precursor producing SOA. The ozone required for the ozonolysis of a-humulene was generated using a corona discharge ozone generator (HTU-500, AZCO Industries LTD) and its concentration was

monitored by an ozone analyzer (Teledyne, T400). Finally, the SOA formation reactions started as soon as the UV lights were turned on in the cycloalkane experiments, while in the CMU chamber when the sesquiterpene was injected.

An important factor that can interfere with an experiment and lead to uncertainty in its results, is the interactions of the pollutants with the walls of the smog chamber. Particle losses to the chamber walls were characterized in each experiment from the seeded period of the experiment (before $t=0$ h) based on the methodology of Hildebrandt et al. (2009). One of the potential complications of the interpretation of the seed-only experiments is coagulation. This process changes the aerosol size distribution and can introduce errors in the loss calculation if neglected. Coagulation was taken into account by using the Aerosol Parameter Estimation (APE) model of Pierce et al. (2008). This approach was first introduced by Nah et al. (2017) and uses the evolution of the particle size distribution, measured by an SMPS, to calculate a size-dependent wall-loss rate constant, corrected for coagulation ($k(D_p)$). This wall rate constant has a plateau in the size range of the AMS mass distributions and therefore to simplify the analysis a size independent average rate constant is used for the AMS mass in this work.

3. Discrepancies between the SMPS and AMS measurements

In this section, the discrepancies between the SMPS and AMS measurements are addressed by presenting in detail the analysis of two experiments (Table 1).

3.1 Nonylcyclohexane oxidation

Figure 1 shows the mass concentrations measured by the SMPS and AMS assuming a density of 1 g cm^{-3} for the SMPS and CE of unity for the AMS. At time zero, when the photooxidation reactions begin and SOA starts to form, the AMS sulfate concentration increases by 73%. This indicates a change in the CE which increases as the SOA coats the ammonium sulfate particles reducing their bounce and enhancing their detection by the AMS (Matthew et al., 2008).

The CE was estimated by averaging the AMS and SMPS distribution every 2 h and using the algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007). Once the lights were turned on, the CE increased from 0.30 ± 0.17 during the seeds-only period to 0.90 ± 0.37 (Figure 2a). The period of the gradual increase corresponds to the period during which the sulfate

concentration increased (Figure 1). The algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007) was applied to two distinct time intervals: the initial two oxidation hours and the final two hours. The estimated SOA density was $0.98 \pm 0.11 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ for both periods. The algorithm can match the distributions relatively well during the seeds only period (Figure 2b). After SOA formation the algorithm matches the distributions for particles smaller than 300 nm but there is a clear discrepancy for larger sizes (Figure 2c).

The composition-dependent algorithm developed by Middlebrook et al. (2012) estimates a CE of 0.39 for the seeds-only period and 0.52 for the reaction period. For these values the aerosol mass concentration is underestimated by 22% for the seeds only period and overestimated by 56% for the SOA formation period.

By applying the estimated values of the CE shown in Figure 2a to the AMS measurements, the concentrations of the different components can be obtained (Figure 2d). The total mass concentrations of the two instruments are in good agreement in both periods. A small deviation of around 8% appears between 0.5 to 2 h. However, the AMS corrected sulfate measurements are clearly discontinuous at 0 h when the CE changes. A reduction of the sulfate concentration by 36% is now estimated. To investigate the reasons for this anomalous behavior the rest of the measurements during the experiment were examined.

The evolution of the number size distribution in this experiment suggests that new particles were formed after the UV lights were turned on and then grew rapidly to sizes of 70 nm to 200 nm (Figure S1). This increase in total number is also clear in the raw and wall-loss corrected measurements of the SMPS, shown in Figure S2.

The mass distributions of the major aerosol components measured by the AMS suggest that the particles smaller than 90 nm (vacuum aerodynamic diameter, D_{va}) are pure SOA (Figure S3). Because of the new particle formation, two different types of particles existed inside the chamber after the reactions started, particles that were pure SOA (new particles) and particles that had a core of ammonium sulfate and a coating of SOA.

3.2 a-Humulene ozonolysis

The mass concentrations measured by SMPS, assuming a density of 1 g cm^{-3} and by AMS, using a CE of unity, are shown in Figure 3a. Similar to the previous experiment, as soon as SOA starts to form, the AMS sulfate concentration increases by 22% because of the CE increase.

The mass distributions (Figure 3b) obtained by both instruments, assuming a density of 1 g cm^{-3} , show the existence of two modes. Based on the AMS measurements the small mode (up to 100 nm) consists of pure SOA. According to the evolution of the number size distribution (Figure S4), new particles were formed in this experiment too.

The algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007) estimates a CE of 0.28 ± 0.10 for the seeds-only period and a CE of 0.30 ± 0.40 for the first hour of the oxidation period. Also, an SOA density of $1.30 \pm 0.85 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ was estimated. The resulting high uncertainties of both the CE and the SOA strongly suggest that there is a fundamental lack of agreement between the measurements of SMPS and AMS even after this size independent correction. The comparison between the measurements of the two instruments can be seen in Figure 4. The use of a single CE fails to bring into agreement the SMPS and AMS measurements, for the first oxidation hour. The corrected AMS volume distribution overestimates the small mode and underestimates the large one.

Utilizing the approach of Middlebrook et al. (2012), a CE of 0.44 and 0.46 is obtained for the seeds-only and reaction period, respectively. When compared to the results of the algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007), the deviation between the measurements of the two instruments increases.

4. Proposed new CE estimation methodology

The observations discussed in the previous section led us to the development of a new methodology for the estimation of CE. Our hypothesis is that the tendency of a particle to bounce on the AMS vaporizer does not automatically change when the first molecules of SOA condense on its surface. We assume that the CE changes from that of the ammonium sulfate to a higher value corresponding to the SOA coated particles when a critical value of the volume ratio of SOA to ammonium sulfate is exceeded. The mobility diameter at which this change happens in a specific experiment, is denoted as D_p^* . This hypothesis means that the CE in an experiment will be both size and composition dependent. Our algorithm determines both the D_p^* and the CE of the different coated particles.

The algorithm developed by Kostenidou et al. (2007) is executed for a selected time period once, for the range of the diameters from the lowest particle size present in the experiment until a user-selected D_p^* and once from D_p^* until the end of the size distribution. As a result, a size dependent CE that follows a step function is assumed. The resulting

AMS and SMPS volume distributions are compared, and their level of agreement is evaluated. The value of the critical mobility diameter (D_p^*) is found through an error minimization process, with different values tested until the two volume distributions are in a good agreement. By improving the CE estimation, the proposed algorithm improves at the same time its estimation of the SOA density in its effort to minimize the discrepancies between the SMPS and AMS measurements.

The CE corrected total mass concentration of ammonium sulfate (M_{AS}) for the selected time period is then calculated as:

$$M_{AS} = \frac{M_{AS(CE=1)}}{(\varphi_{AS} CE)_{D_p < D_p^*} + (\varphi_{AS} CE)_{D_p > D_p^*}} \quad (1)$$

where the $M_{AS(CE=1)}$ is the mass concentration of ammonium sulfate measured by the AMS with a collection efficiency of 1 and φ_{AS} is the volume fraction of ammonium sulfate for the selected time period. φ_{AS} is calculated from the volume concentration of ammonium sulfate and the volume concentration of the total aerosol. The subscripts $D_p < D_p^*$ and $D_p > D_p^*$ indicate the particles with diameters lower or higher than the critical one, respectively. The AMS volume distribution is calculated from the AMS mass distributions, using the known density of ammonium sulfate (1.77 g cm^{-3}) and the SOA density which is estimated by the algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007).

The CE corrected mass concentration of SOA (M_{SOA}) for the selected time period is estimated by:

$$M_{SOA} = \frac{M_{SOA(CE=1)}}{(\varphi_{SOA} CE)_{D_p < D_p^*} + (\varphi_{SOA} CE)_{D_p > D_p^*}} \quad (2)$$

where the AMS-measured total mass concentration of SOA, denoted as $M_{SOA(CE=1)}$ corresponds to a collection efficiency of 1 and φ_{SOA} is the volume fraction of SOA. The denominators of Equation (1) and (2) can be viewed as the effective CE of ammonium sulfate and SOA, respectively.

5. Application of the new CE estimation algorithm

5.1 Nonylcyclohexane oxidation

Following the steps of the proposed methodology, the density of SOA was estimated to be equal to $1.38 \pm 0.12 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ for both modes and a critical mobility diameter of 300 nm was found for the full reaction period. The estimated composition dependent CE for the reaction period is:

$$CE = \begin{cases} 0.95 \pm 0.10, & D_p < 300 \text{ nm} \\ 0.55 \pm 0.07, & D_p > 300 \text{ nm} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The effective CE of ammonium sulfate is estimated to be 0.55 and of SOA 0.96. This shows that the hypothesis of the same CE for all species in this experiment will introduce significant errors. Also, the use of the sulfate/OA ratio (without corrections) can lead to problems.

The size of 300 nm was found as the optimal D_p^* , due to the minimal average absolute deviation exhibited between the two instruments (Figure S5). The volume ratio of SOA to ammonium sulfate for this experiment was equal to 1 at 300 nm (Figure S6). Particles with sizes below 300 nm had a ratio of V_{SOA}/V_{seeds} higher than 1 while above 300 nm the ratio was less than 1. The coating thickness of the particles with diameter D_p^* was estimated to be 35 nm, assuming a core-shell morphology.

The resulting volume distributions of the two instruments are in a better agreement (Figure 5a) than the corresponding ones of Figure 2c.

The SMPS and AMS CE corrected volume concentrations are given in Figure 5b. The concentrations of ammonium and sulfate, corrected with the new approach, change smoothly at time zero. The corrected AMS and SMPS volume concentrations show good agreement (average deviation of 4%). The results shown in Figure 5b have not been corrected for particle losses to the walls of the chamber. The use of a size-dependent CE influences the slope of the AMS concentration AMS measurements as one can see comparing Figure 1 with 5b. This is due to changes of the aerosol size distribution and morphology (coating thickness) over time, that changes the effective CE applied on the concentrations of the various aerosol components.

To calculate the AMS-based SOA after correcting the measurements with the CE and wall losses, the small quantity of OA that exists before $t=0$ h (see Figure 5b) is subtracted from the total mass concentration. For the SMPS-based SOA before correcting

with the estimated SOA density and after applying the wall-loss corrections, the volume concentration of seeds is estimated and is subtracted from the total volume concentration. The SOA mass concentrations obtained from both instruments also have an average deviation of 4% (Figure S7). This indicates a good level of agreement between the two measurements after the applied corrections. These concentrations have been corrected for particle losses to the chamber walls using a size-dependent wall-loss rate constant (Figure S8). In the case of AMS, a size independent wall-loss rate constant of 0.032 h^{-1} is used. This value corresponds to the plateau of the $k(D_p)$ profile, approximately for $D_p > 100 \text{ nm}$ and corresponds to practically all the range of the AMS mass distribution.

5.2 a-Humulene ozonolysis

Using the proposed approach, for the reaction period the estimated SOA density was found equal to $1.15 \pm 0.05 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and the composition dependent CE is:

$$CE = \begin{cases} 0.57 \pm 0.06, & D_p < 130 \text{ nm} \\ 0.34 \pm 0.09, & D_p > 130 \text{ nm} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The effective CE of ammonium sulfate is estimated equal to 0.33 and 0.64 for the SOA during the reaction period. In both experiments, as expected based on the particle properties, the effective CE of ammonium sulfate is smaller than the one of SOA. The corresponding CE values are different in the two experiments due to the formation of different SOA which coats the ammonium sulfate particles and due to the two different AMS units used. A critical mobility diameter of 130 nm that corresponds to a volume ratio of SOA to ammonium sulfate equal to 3 was found (Figure S9). This threshold diameter is not directly related to the point at which the AMS curves cross. They are calculated by minimizing the discrepancy between the AMS and SMPS distributions (Figure S10).

The agreement of the average volume distributions from 0 to 6 h measured by the two instruments after correcting the AMS data based on the proposed methodology can be seen in Figure 6a. The Aitken mode CE increased from 0.30 to 0.57 using the new approach, leading to a notable decrease in the corrected volume concentration of the AMS for the corresponding particle sizes, as evident in Figure 6a when compared to Figure 4b. Now both instruments agree that there was a smaller first mode with organic particles

formed by nucleation and growth and a seed layer mode containing SOA coated ammonium sulfate particles.

The corrected AMS measurements, along with the SMPS values, are shown in Figure 6b. The total volume concentrations of the two instruments are in a good agreement as the AMS has an average deviation of 2% from the SMPS during the reaction period.

After accounting for wall losses, the calculated SOA mass concentrations from both SMPS and AMS devices differed by 3% (Figure S11). The SMPS was corrected for wall-losses using the coagulation corrected wall-loss rate constant of Figure S12. For the AMS wall-loss correction, a size independent wall-loss rate constant of 0.29 h^{-1} was used. This value was obtained from averaging the calculated $k(D_p)$ profile over the AMS distribution size range.

The reported SOA production shows a rapid increase in the first 10 min of the oxidation period. Throughout the remaining reaction period, the concentration of SOA continues to increase. These results are consistent with the conclusions of Sippial et al. (2023). Their study indicated that this rapid increase is primarily driven by the fast reaction of ozone with the first double bond of α -humulene. However, the subsequent reactions involving the second and third double bonds occur at a slower rate, resulting in a sustained production of SOA.

6. Conclusions

In this study, the disagreement of AMS measurements compared to the SMPS, for chamber-generated SOA, was investigated. The raw measurements of the two instruments exhibit discrepancies attributed to the CE issues of the AMS and the uncertain density of the SOA formed.

The current approach of a size independent CE, failed to close the gap between the AMS and SMPS measurements, in both presented experiments, with the algorithm of Middlebrook et al. (2012) leading to even higher deviations than the one by Kostenidou et al. (2007). This gap was more pronounced in experiments in which seeds were used but nucleation also took place. This resulted in two particle populations, one consisting of just SOA and one with ammonium sulfate coated with SOA.

Our observations can be explained by assuming that there is a critical diameter at which the volume ratio of SOA to ammonium sulfate surpasses a critical threshold and

the CE changes. As a result, the tendency of a particle to bounce on the AMS vaporizer is a function of the SOA concentration within the particle. Thus, particles with sizes that exceed D_p^* have a lower CE than those with smaller sizes in our experiments.

A new method for the estimation of a composition- and thus size-dependent CE has been developed. Overall, the proposed methodology shows a good performance in matching the measurements of the two instruments and in estimating the produced SOA in both experiments. The corrected measurements had an average deviation smaller than 10% both in the total mass concentration and the SOA formed.

The proposed methodology had satisfactory results for SOA laboratory measurements. However further investigation is required to determine whether this methodology can yield accurate and reliable results for ambient measurements where the aerosol is a lot more complex. The methodology can be further extended in the future by adopting a more complex functional form of the dependence of the CE on composition compared to the step function that has been used in this study. This step function is a compromise between simplicity and realism, and it appears that it is sufficient for the improvement of the algorithm.

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Data availability statement

The measurements that support the findings of this study are available on request from Spyros Pandis (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr)

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7. References

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Table 1. Experimental conditions.

Precursor	VOC (ppb)	[OH] $\times 10^7$ (molecule cm^{-3})	O ₃ (ppb)	Seeds ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	SOA ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
Nonylcyclohexane (Exp. 1)	58	2	-	35	29.7 \pm 0.1
A-humulene (Exp. 2)	12	-	290	116	49.1 \pm 1.4

Figure 1. Mass concentration time series of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane) by the SMPS (black), AMS (grey) and the AMS-measured composition. A CE=1 is assumed for the AMS and a density of 1 g cm^{-3} for the SMPS. The shaded area indicates that the chamber was dark.

Figure 2. The algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007) generates for Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane) (a) a size independent collection efficiency as a function of time and uses it to the following results, for the (b) seeds-only (-2.9 to 0 h) ($CE = 0.30 \pm 0.17$) (c) reaction period (0 to 4 h) ($CE = 0.90 \pm 0.37$), the average volume size distributions of SMPS (black) and AMS (red) and (d) mass concentration time series, of the total measured by SMPS (black), AMS (grey) and of the AMS-measured composition. The shaded area indicates that the chamber was dark. The data are not corrected for particle wall losses.

Figure 3. For Exp. 2 (a-humulene) (a) mass concentration time series of the total measured by SMPS (black), AMS (grey) and of the AMS-measured composition and (b) average mass distribution of SMPS (black line) and of AMS for each species, from 0 to 1 h, as a function of the mobility diameter. A $\text{CE}=1$ is used for the AMS and a density of 1 g cm^{-3} for the SMPS.

Figure 4. Average volume size distributions of SMPS (black) and AMS (red) of Exp. 2 (a-humulene), corrected with the currently used algorithm, for the (a) seeds-only (-3 to 0 h) (b) reaction period (0 to 1 h). A CE of 0.28 ± 0.1 and 0.3 ± 0.4 was used, respectively.

Figure 5. (a) Average volume size distributions of SMPS (black) and AMS (red) for the reaction period and (b) volume concentration time series of the total measured by SMPS (black), AMS (grey) and of the AMS-measured composition, of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane), corrected with the new approach. The shaded area indicates that the chamber was dark. The data are not corrected for particle wall losses.

Figure 6. (a) Average volume size distributions of SMPS (black) and AMS (red) for the reaction period and (b) volume concentration time series of the total measured by SMPS (black), AMS (grey) and of the AMS-measured composition, of Exp. 2 (a-humulene), corrected with the new approach.

Supplementary Material

Figure S1. Particle number size distribution as a function of time for Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane).

Figure S2. The SMPS-measured (black line) and the particle wall-loss corrected number concentration (red line) of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane). The shaded area indicates that the chamber was dark.

Figure S3. Average mass distribution of each species, measured by the AMS for the UV-On period of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane), as a function of vacuum aerodynamic diameter.

Figure S4. Particle number size distribution as a function of time for Exp. 2 (a-humulene).

Figure S5. Average absolute deviation of the AMS volume concentration, corrected with the new approach, from the SMPS, for different critical mobility diameters of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane), for the period of 0 h to 1 h.

Figure S6. Average volume ratio of SOA to ammonium sulfate of Exp.1 (nonylcyclohexane), as a function of mobility diameter. The dotted line corresponds to the critical mobility diameter (D_p^*).

Figure S7. Wall-loss corrected SOA mass concentrations time series of SMPS and AMS, also corrected with the new approach, of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane). The shaded area indicates that the chamber was dark.

Figure S8. Size dependent particle wall-loss rate constant profile (red line), corrected for coagulation of Exp. 1 (nonylcyclohexane).

Figure S9. Average volume ratio of SOA to ammonium sulfate of Exp.2 (a-humulene), as a function of mobility diameter. The dotted line corresponds to the critical mobility diameter (D_p^*).

In experiment 2, the selection of the critical diameter was relatively straightforward compared to the first. Only the 130 nm as D_p^* , exhibited good agreement between the volume distributions of AMS and SMPS. This is supported by the error score that resulted from the algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007) given in Figure S10. Among the tested diameters, the 130 nm has the smallest error score. The 200 nm diameter had a similar error score but was not chosen as the critical diameter due to less agreement between the smaller modes of the two instruments. Diameters below 130 nm were not considered as there was no match between the volume distributions from the two instruments using the provided code.

Figure S10. Error score of the algorithm of Kostenidou et al. (2007) as a function of different critical mobility diameters, of Exp. 2 (a-humulene).

Figure S11. Wall-loss corrected SOA mass concentrations time series of SMPS and AMS, also corrected with the new approach, of Exp. 2 (a-humulene).

Figure S12. Size dependent particle wall-loss rate constant profile (red line), corrected for coagulation of Exp. 2 (a-humulene).